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**Quality Management of Educational Programs in the Field of Children's
Talent Development for the Film Industry**

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***Abstract.** The quality management of programs in the field of children's talent development for the film industry is a relevant area in the modern system of education and culture. Given the rapid development of media and digital technologies and the growing demand for highly qualified specialists in this field, it is important to pay special attention to the quality of training of the younger generation who show abilities in acting, directing, screenwriting, editing and other related fields. It is at this stage of childhood that creative thinking, basic professional skills, communication skills and self-confidence are formed, which further determines the success of a child as a future participant in the film process. The **purpose of the study** is to analyze educational programs in the film industry and develop recommendations for improving their level, in particular, through the*

introduction of new teaching methods and technologies. **Methods.** To solve the tasks, we used a systematic approach, comparative analysis, interviews with industry experts, and analysis of practical situations. **Results.** It has been shown that quality management of educational programs for the development of children's talents in the film industry requires clear criteria that take into account not only academic knowledge but also practical skills, creativity and emotional balance of students. Individualization is a key element of education, as it allows us to take into account the characteristics of each child. Collaboration with industry professionals and participation in real-world projects is a valuable experience for children, and the assessment of results should include not only theoretical knowledge but also creative and practical achievements. Psychological support and the integration of the latest technologies into education are also important components of successful talent development. The involvement of parents and mentors in the learning process helps to maintain students' motivation and emotional stability. **Conclusions.** Thus, effective quality management of educational programs in the field of child talent development for the film industry requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account both academic and practical aspects of education. Programs should be flexible and focused on the individual needs of students to best unleash their potential and creativity. An important component is cooperation with film industry professionals, which gives children the opportunity to gain practical experience and a deeper understanding of the industry's requirements.

Keywords: innovative methods, gamification, psychological support, practical experience, internship programs, competitiveness, cinematography, personnel training.

Управління якістю освітніх програм у сфері розвитку дитячих талантів для кіноіндустрії

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***Анотація.** Управління якістю програм у сфері розвитку дитячих талантів для кіноіндустрії є актуальним напрямом у сучасній системі освіти та культури. Із огляду на стрімкий розвиток медіа, цифрових технологій та зростання попиту на висококваліфікованих фахівців у цій сфері, важливо приділяти особливу увагу якості підготовки молодого покоління, яке виявляє здібності до акторського мистецтва, режисури, сценаристики, монтажу та інших суміжних галузей. Саме на етапі дитинства формується творче мислення, базові професійні навички, комунікаційні здібності та впевненість у собі, що в подальшому визначає успішність дитини як майбутнього учасника кінопроцесу. **Мета** роботи – аналіз освітніх програм у кіноіндустрії й розробка рекомендацій щодо покращення їхнього рівня, зокрема, через впровадження нових навчальних методів та технологій. **Методи.** Для вирішення поставлених завдань використовувалися методи системного підходу, порівняльного аналізу, інтерв'ювання експертів галузі та розбір практичних ситуацій. **Результати.** Показано, що управління якістю освітніх програм для розвитку дитячих талантів у кіноіндустрії вимагає чітких критеріїв, що враховують не лише академічні знання, а й практичні навички, творчий хист та емоційну рівновагу учнів. Індивідуалізація є ключовим*

елементом навчання, бо дозволяє брати до уваги особливості кожної дитини. Співпраця з професіоналами галузі та участь у реальних проєктах є цінним досвідом для дітей, а оцінка результатів має включати не тільки теоретичні знання, а й креативні та практичні досягнення. Психологічна підтримка та інтеграція новітніх технологій у навчання також є важливими складовими для успішного розвитку талантів. Залучення батьків та наставників до процесу навчання сприяє підтримці мотивації й емоційної стабільності учнів.

Висновки. Таким чином, ефективне управління якістю освітніх програм у сфері розвитку дитячих талантів для кіноіндустрії передбачає комплексний підхід, що враховує як академічні, так і практичні аспекти навчання. Програми повинні бути гнучкими, орієнтованими на індивідуальні потреби учнів, щоб якнайкраще розкривати їхній потенціал і творчі здібності. Важливою складовою є співпраця з професіоналами кіноіндустрії, що надає дітям можливість отримати практичний досвід і глибше зрозуміти вимоги галузі.

Ключові слова: інноваційні методики, гейміфікація, психологічна підтримка, практичний досвід, програми стажування, конкурентоспроможність, кінематографія, підготовка кадрів.

Problem statement. Given the continuous changes and development of the film industry, there is an urgent need to train new generations of gifted children who will be able to realize their potential in this field. However, modern educational programs aimed at developing children's talents in cinema do not always meet the requirements of the professional industry. The main problem is the lack of clear quality standards for educational courses, which prevents them from taking into account the individual characteristics and abilities of each child. Most programs

offer a one-size-fits-all approach to learning that does not allow for the full development of students' creative skills, particularly in specialized areas such as acting or scriptwriting.

The lack of modern technologies and advanced teaching methods, such as digital tools such as 3D animation, virtual reality, or digital editing, significantly reduces students' ability to acquire key skills in the film industry. Another significant problem is the lack of practical interaction with industry professionals, which distances theoretical knowledge from the real requirements of the film market. As a result, many students do not acquire the practical skills necessary for a successful career. Most educational programs do not pay enough attention to psychological aspects, which are critical for children who dream of a career in such a busy and stressful field as cinema. Psychological support, the ability to adapt to change, and emotional resilience are essential for young talent to be able to effectively deal with the pressure, stress, and criticism that are inevitable in film production.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Problems related to the development of contemporary Ukrainian cinema are actively studied in scientific papers and articles. In particular, T. Kulyk [1] examines various genres of Ukrainian cinema that reflect important trends in the evolution of domestic cinema, which in turn sets the goal of improving the quality management system of educational programs to develop children's talents in the film industry. L. Yepyk and D. Yepyk [2] studied the impact of contemporary Ukrainian cinema on the formation of national consciousness, emphasizing the importance of cinema as a powerful tool in developing national identity, cultural values and social beliefs. K. Postova [3] analyzes the peculiarities of combining formal and non-formal education in curricula for gifted students, assessing their effectiveness and impact on the development of children's abilities. S. Pogasiy [4] studies the peculiarities of Ukrainian author's

cinema, which not only reflects the socio-cultural realities of the country but also opens up new prospects for developing children's talents in cinema, emphasizing the importance of introducing national values into the creative process. H. Pohrebniak [5] analyzes the stages of the author's cinema development, emphasizing the importance of considering cultural changes in curricula to develop children's talents in cinema. O. Bezruchko and N. Kachmar [6] explore the main trends and problems Ukrainian cinema faces in the current context. S. Derevianko [7] examines in detail the processes of developing children's creative abilities, emphasizing the identification and support of talent in various fields, including art and cinema. A. Klepatska [8], in her work “Advice to Parents on Raising a Creatively Gifted Child in the Family,” analyzes the main approaches to supporting and developing children's creative abilities in the context of family education. S. Harbar and M. Vozniuk [9] studied how animation technologies affect the development of creative and cognitive abilities in children. In the course of lectures “Stage and Screen Art with Teaching Methods” for students of specialty 013 “Primary Education”, authored by N. Bryzhak [10], the importance of integrating stage and screen art into the educational process, especially in the context of primary education, is emphasized. K. Guz [11] emphasizes the importance of a holistic content approach in forming youth talent. Teacher T. Konivitska [12] presents a comprehensive analysis of the history of the film industry in her practice-oriented publication, which can be a valuable tool in developing cultural and educational programs aimed at forming national identity through visual art. The methodological materials of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine [13] raise the issue of national-patriotic education as one of the key areas of modern educational policy.

O. Nozdrachova [14] considers the role of the teacher as a facilitator in working with gifted children, drawing attention to the need for an individual

approach and creating conditions for students' self-realization. L. Petelko [15] explores ways to develop preschoolers' abilities and creative potential, emphasizing the importance of early identification of giftedness and the formation of value orientations through educational and cultural practices.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. We can highlight several important points from the preceding discussion that require deeper study and improvement. Firstly, there is insufficient consideration of the specifics of film education for children given Ukrainian cultural and social conditions, which hinders the development of national talent. Secondly, there are no holistic approaches to combining theoretical and practical knowledge of film education, which is a drawback in preparing children for professional work in film. In addition, the effectiveness of existing methods of developing creative abilities in cinema remains insufficiently researched, which requires updating curricula and courses to train qualified professionals. These issues require further research and the development of new approaches to improving the quality of educational programs to develop children's talents in cinema.

Formulation of the article's objectives. Given the urgency of this issue, the article aims to study the problem of the quality of educational programs in the field of developing children's talents for the film industry and to outline key areas for their improvement, taking into account cultural, social and technological changes. The article aims to identify effective methods and approaches to teaching young filmmakers, as well as to develop advice on how to integrate theoretical and practical aspects of cinematography into the educational process in order to support and develop the creative abilities of children who have the prospect of a successful career in the film industry.

The main objectives of the article are:

1. Assessment of the current state of educational programs for developing children's talents in the film industry.
2. Identification of the main problems in the curricula of this area.
3. Formulating recommendations for improving teaching methods.
4. Developing ways to combine theoretical and practical aspects of cinematography in the educational process.

Summary of the main research material. Education in the film industry, especially in training children, is a complex and multifaceted process encompassing artistic, technical, psychological and pedagogical aspects. With the rapid progress of cinematography and digital technologies, the quality of educational programs for young talents is becoming important in their future ability to compete at the professional level. Effective management of such programs requires a systematic approach, including standardization of educational materials, introducing innovative methods, forming a competency-based learning model, and integrating modern technologies into the learning process.

The need for creativity is one of a modern person's most important motivational aspirations since life in the new information dimension increasingly requires the rejection of templates, the development of creativity and individuality in solving any problems. The most important factor in forming these qualities is the age period of preschool childhood; this period is sensitive to the development of creative abilities [7, p. 4]. Gifted children who want to succeed in cinema must be prepared for physical and technical difficulties and emotional challenges. They must learn to express and convey their feelings through the lens, creating sincere and lively characters with whom the audience can establish emotional contact.

Educational programs for children aimed at discovering talent in film should cover various areas of cinema, including acting and key components of film production such as cinematography, editing, sound recording and other technical aspects. Such a comprehensive approach will allow children to better understand how the cinematic system works and why each team member plays an important role in creating a quality film product.

The most important thing in children's education is maintaining emotional stability and adapting because working in film is often accompanied by significant stress and difficult conditions. Children involved in filming should be prepared for long working days, difficult circumstances, and fatigue and be able to react quickly to changes in the script or director's instructions. They must be able to focus on their work and not let external factors affect the result. Considering these aspects, educational programs for children with acting and film talent should be versatile and flexible. They should combine the development of both technical and creative abilities while providing opportunities for psycho-emotional development. This will enable children not only to master the creation of art but also to prepare them for the challenges they may face in the film industry.

Teachers know that a child is a natural actor who constantly plays a role in children's play [10, p. 31]. Through play, children understand social roles and develop the ability to express themselves creatively, as well as their imagination and sensitivity to emotions. These properties are the basis for further improvement of acting and other creative abilities. Incorporating elements of theater, role-playing, or drama into the learning process helps develop creativity, adaptability, and teamwork, which are essential for success in the film industry.

H. Bryzhak emphasizes [10, p. 32] that for the effective development of acting skills, it is important to focus on the following aspects:

- teach children to intonate sentences, identify the main characters, and read a story in person;
- teach children to stage plays;
- teaching how to write scenarios based on what they have read;
- to enrich students' vocabulary;
- to develop children's acting skills and creative imagination;
- to cultivate a love for the native word and theater and support cognitive interest.

In addition, the teacher should take into account certain principles of developing the creative abilities of a young person:

- the principle of consistency;
- the principle of individualization, skill and accessibility;
- the principle of an integrated approach to work [10, p. 30].

To guarantee high-quality education in the field of cinema, a comprehensive approach should be used (Table 1) based on several basic principles. First of all, a competency-based approach is important, and it is based not only on theoretical knowledge but also on practical skills that are essential for professional work in the film industry. A highly professional teaching staff is a key factor in developing high-quality educational programs.

Table 1

Strategies and tools for managing the development of children's talents in film education

Main directions	Management methods and tools	Goals and expected results
Evaluation and analysis of existing educational programs	Comparison of programs with international standards, survey of participants	Increasing the compliance of programs with modern

		requirements of the film industry
Selection and training of highly qualified mentors	Conducting attestations, analyzing the experience of teachers	Building a qualified team of mentors
Development of training materials and courses	Use of modern technologies, development of interactive courses	Creating high-quality, innovative learning resources
Monitoring and evaluation of learning outcomes	Monitoring student progress, testing, feedback	Ensuring the development of personal and professional skills of children in the film industry

Source: author's own development

Professionalization of the educational process requires the involvement of film industry professionals, such as directors, screenwriters, producers, and other professionals with practical experience in the film industry.

It is also important to have the support of mentors, which allows for an individual approach to the development of each child's talents. N. Bryzhak believes [10] that the degree of effectiveness of pedagogical work depends on the innate and acquired individual qualities of the subject. Pedagogical artistry is a certain set of qualities that ensure the effectiveness of the educational process and, therefore, requires special work aimed at their development. This work, like any other, is aimed at developing the teacher's pedagogical skills and should begin with the identification of abilities that will ensure the successful mastery of a particular component of the pedagogical technique in the future. Artistry is a whole complex of personality qualities necessary for a teacher (animator) in a professional activity: expressiveness of words, gestures, power of influence on the audience, richness of

emotions and ability to control them, creative activity, imaginative thinking, originality, focus on aesthetic and spiritual ideals [10, p. 22].

One of the key challenges for film education programs is the insufficient inclusion of practical experience in the educational process. This situation complicates the adaptation of graduates to work on film sets, where they are expected not only to know the theoretical foundations but also to be able to use this knowledge effectively in a changing and unpredictable professional reality. To address this issue, a comprehensive approach should be taken, which involves strengthening cooperation between educational institutions and the film industry, including film companies, theater studios, production centers, and other organizations involved in film production. This will allow children not only to learn about cinema as an art form but also to acquire skills that will help them succeed in this field. This approach will help educate professionals who can quickly adapt to changes in the film market and gain competitive advantages.

Another important aspect of developing young talent in the film industry is psychological preparation for the challenges they face in such a competitive, volatile and stressful field as filmmaking. Young people who want to pursue a film career often experience significant psychological pressure: constant uncertainty, the need to participate in numerous auditions, long waiting periods that can be emotionally draining, and working under the pressure of rush shoots and the publicity that often accompanies a star career. Therefore, educational programs for future actors should include components that promote the development of psychological resilience, as these skills directly affect their ability to adapt to stressful situations and maintain a high level of performance on set. It is also important to integrate training to develop self-esteem and self-awareness into the educational process, as confidence is

extremely important for success in such a competitive and subjective field, the film industry.

Modern challenges in education, especially in training future actors and film professionals, require introducing advanced digital technologies (Table 2). Innovations open up new opportunities in the process of acquiring knowledge, as well as help to adapt curricula to modern needs and increase their effectiveness.

One of the best ways to develop educational programs for children in film is to use dual education, which combines theoretical training with practical training and experience in real-life film production environments. Dual education allows children to gain practical experience through direct interaction with film professionals, accelerating their adaptation to the profession's requirements and improving the quality of their training.

Stable interaction between educational institutions and film production companies creates an educational environment as close as possible to the realities of the creative process. Working directly with real film crews on film sets is an important step in their development.

Table 2

Digital tools for developing children's talents in the film industry

Digital technologies	Methods of use in education and development	Benefits for the development of children's talents	Application examples
Virtual reality (VR)	Creating interactive learning environments	Immersion in real movie scenarios, development of acting skills	Virtual scenes, simulation of acting roles
Augmented reality (AR)	Interactive lessons and training in a real environment	Visualize movie scripts, practice expressions and gestures	Complementing acting lessons in AR format
Multimedia platforms and online courses	Distance learning, access to video tutorials and trainings	Convenient access to training materials and resources	Online courses in acting, film editing

3D modeling and animation	Creating animations, 3D models, special effects	Development of creative thinking, learning the basics of film production	Character animation, creation of 3D scenes and special effects
Social networks and digital platforms	Promotion of children's talents in the film industry	Disseminating creative works, attracting attention to potential talents	TikTok, YouTube for video publishing, interaction with fans
Mobile applications for learning	Development of applications for improving acting skills	Accessibility of training at any stage, time flexibility	Applications for developing stage images, improving diction
Artificial intelligence (AI) for speech analysis	Using AI to analyze and improve role performance	Analysis of expressions, facial expressions, emotional play of actors	Identification of strengths and weaknesses in role performance
Digital studios for editing and post-production	Using video editing software	Development of technical skills in film and video production	Using programs such as Adobe Premiere, Final Cut Pro

Source: compiled by the author

The hands-on approach not only helps them understand the technical intricacies of production but also allows them to master the social and psychological aspects of teamwork and improve their communication and emotional management skills under pressure. Cooperation between schools and film studios opens the door for children to understand film production. This interaction gives students the opportunity to practice under the guidance of professionals. This not only allows them to apply theory in practice but also provides a unique experience of working under pressure and creative inspiration. At the same time, such activities contribute to the development of psychological endurance, which is important for successful work in a field that often requires quick decision-making and stressful conditions.

The integration of curricula with real film projects contributes to the comprehensive development of key skills necessary for successful work in the film

industry. The involvement of children in practical activities in the field of film production not only allows them to develop creative thinking but also builds critical skills such as effective teamwork, constructive communication, responsibility, time management, and the ability to adapt quickly to the dynamic conditions of the production process.

By working on real projects in collaboration with experienced film industry professionals, students gain valuable practical experience, learn to understand the specifics of the filming process and the distribution of roles in the film crew and master the skills of solving creative and technical problems in real-time. This approach not only broadens professional horizons but also helps to develop a deeper understanding of the structure of film production as a team-based, creative and technologically complex industry.

Conclusions. Thus, high-quality educational programs aimed at developing children's talents in the field of cinema are formed through a holistic approach that combines educational content with practical immersion in a professional environment. To effectively train future professionals, theoretical knowledge alone is not enough; constant contact with the dynamic reality of the film industry, which requires flexibility, creativity, and social skills, is necessary. The educational process in this area should be lively, adaptive and open to change.

Professional development in the creative industries is inextricably linked to psychological resilience and emotional literacy. That is why an important aspect of quality training is the integration of psychological support, which helps young talents not only to reveal their abilities but also to respond effectively to stressful situations, competition, and pressure inherent in the professional environment. This approach contributes to the formation of an internal resource necessary for the sustainable development of a personality under high emotional stress.

Modern film education is impossible without the active use of digital tools and technologies. They not only expand the possibilities of interaction with educational material but also make the educational process more practice-oriented, exciting and closer to professional conditions. All of this creates the basis for the formation of competitive, emotionally mature and technologically prepared young professionals of the modern film industry.

Approaches to creating high-quality educational programs aimed at developing children's talent in the film industry should be comprehensive and flexible. Training courses should include not only professional training but also promote the development of psychological and social skills. This will allow children to successfully adapt to the modern requirements of film production and confidently overcome its challenges.

List of references:

1. Кулик Т. Сучасне українське кіно: інструкція з користування. URL: <https://cutt.ly/ggBswig> (дата звернення: 11.01.2025).
2. Єпик Л., Єпик Д. Сучасне українське кіно як фактор формування національної свідомості. *Knowledge, Education, Law, Management*. 2020. Т. 2, № 3 (31). С. 32–36. URL: <https://kelmczasopisma.com/en/viewpdf/1136> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
3. Постова К. Освітні програми для обдарованих учнів в умовах інтеграції формальної та неформальної освіти. *Обдаровані діти – скарб нації: матеріали II міжнар. наук.-практ. онлайн-конф.*. 2021. С. 422–426. URL: <https://surl.li/xyalkj> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
4. Погасій С. Національна специфіка українського авторського кіно. *Культурологічний альманах*. 2024. № 1 (9). С. 355–365. URL:

<https://almanac.npu.kiev.ua/index.php/almanac/article/view/357/335> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

5. Погребняк Г. Авторський кінематограф у культурному просторі другої половини ХХ – початку ХХІ століття: монографія. Київ: НАКККиМ, 2020. 448 с. URL: <https://surl.lu/jzvnci> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

6. Bezruchko O., Kachmar N. The development of contemporary Ukrainian cinema. *Вісник Київського національного університету культури і мистецтв. Серія: Аудіовізуальне мистецтво і виробництво*. 2021. №. 4(2). С. 208–216. URL: <http://audiovisual-art.knukim.edu.ua/article/view/248680/246339> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

7. Дерев'янка С. Психологія дитячої творчості: навчально-методичні рекомендації. Чернігів: НУЧК імені Т.Г. Шевченка, 2020. 76 с. URL: <https://surl.li/rhargu> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

8. Клепацька А. Поради батькам щодо виховання творчо обдарованої дитини в сім'ї. *Fundamental and Applied Research in the Modern World*. Boston, USA, 2021. P. 425–433. URL: <https://surl.li/zfoqgg> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

9. Гарбар С., Вознюк М. Мультиплікаційні засоби як чинник розвитку дітей дошкільного віку. *Fundamental and Applied Research in the Modern World*. Boston, USA, 2021. P. 250–257. URL: <https://surl.li/etbutb> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

10. Сценічне та екранне мистецтво з методикою навчання: курс лекцій для здобувачів спеціальності 013 «Початкова освіта», укл. Н. Брижак. Мукачєво: МДУ, 2024. 55 с. URL: http://dspace-s.msu.edu.ua:8080/bitstream/123456789/11887/1/STAGE_AND_SCREEN.pdf (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).

11. Гуз К. Роль цілісності змісту освіти у формуванні обдарованості учнів. *Обдаровані діти – скарб нації*: матеріали II міжнар. наук.-практ. онлайн-конф. 2021. С. 172–175. URL: <https://surl.li/ffcczh> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
12. Конівіцька Т. Історія кіно: навчальний посібник для студентів та курсантів усіх спеціальностей. Львів: ГАЛИЧ-ПРЕС, 2024. 264 с. URL: <https://surl.li/fasrne> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
13. Національно-патріотичне виховання. Міністерство освіти і науки України. URL: <https://cutt.ly/VgVfP0n> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
14. Ноздрачова О. Вчитель для обдарованих дітей як фасилітатор їх розвитку. *Обдаровані діти – скарб нації*: матеріали II міжнар. наук.-практ. онлайн-конф. 2021. С. 365–368. URL: <https://surl.li/awpzsv> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).
15. Петелько Л. Розвиток здібностей та творчих можливостей у вихованців закладів дошкільної освіти. *Обдаровані діти – скарб нації*: матеріали II міжнар. наук.-практ. онлайн-конф.. 2021. С. 386–389. URL: <https://surl.li/kssqar> (дата звернення: 01.02.2025).